

Density and viscosity studies of glucose solutions in water and in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr solutions at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K

Pandharinath S. Nikam, Mehdi Hasan*, Kailas H. Kapadnis^a and Thansing B. Pawar

P.G. Department of Physical Chemistry, M.S.G. College, Malegaon Camp-423 105, Dist. Nashik, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : mihasan@rediffmail.com

^aL.V.H. College, Nashik, Maharashtra, India

Manuscript received 11 October 2007, revised 5 August 2008, accepted 7 August 2008

Abstract : The densities and viscosities of glucose solutions in water and in 0.05, 0.1, 0.5, 1.00 M NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr have been measured at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. From densities (ρ), the limiting partial molar volumes (ϕ_v^0) have been evaluated. The viscosity data have been analyzed with the help of the modified Jones-Dole equation and the corresponding viscosity B -coefficients have been calculated.

Keywords : Viscosity, glucose solution, density, Jones-Dole equation.

Introduction

Studies on thermodynamic properties have been made on aqueous ternary systems containing carbohydrates and electrolytes from this laboratory¹⁻⁴. It has been reported earlier^{5,6} that mono and disaccharides are structure makers, suggesting hydrogen bonding with OH groups of sugars with water. It would be interesting to examine whether the structure modification of water by these sugars gets enhanced or subdued in presence of an ion. In the present paper we report limiting apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v^0), experimental slopes (S_v) and viscosity B -coefficients which have been interpreted in terms of solute-solvent and solute-solute interactions.

Results and discussion

The measured ρ values of glucose solutions in water and in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr solutions at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K are used to calculate the apparent molar volumes ϕ_v using the equation

$$\phi_v = [1000(\rho_0 - \rho)/(C \times \rho_0)] + (M/\rho_0) \quad (1)$$

where ρ and ρ_0 are the densities of solution and solvent respectively, M , is the molecular weight of the solute, C , is the concentration in mol L⁻¹. The ϕ_v values varied linearly with the concentration in conformity with Redlich-Mayer equation as reported earlier by Nikam *et al.*¹⁻⁴. Fig. 1 gives representative graphs of ϕ_v versus C for

Fig. 1. ϕ_v versus C for glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl at 298.15 K : (◆) 0 M NaCl; (■) 0.05 M NaCl; (▲) 0.1 M NaCl; (×) 0.5 M NaCl; (*) 1 M NaCl.

glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl at 298.15 K. The limiting partial molar volume of glucose in aqueous electrolyte solutions were obtained by computerized least-

Table 1. ϕ_v^0 and S_v values of glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr solutions at different temperatures

Glucose solution in	ϕ_v^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)				S_v (cm ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{3/2})			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
Water	112.07	112.48	113.08	113.62	34.01	36.05	37.41	38.09
0.05 M NaCl	113.11	113.51	114.11	114.65	34.26	36.28	37.63	38.22
0.1 M NaCl	114.14	114.58	115.18	115.70	34.68	36.68	37.93	38.53
0.5 M NaCl	116.26	116.70	117.30	117.82	34.74	36.96	38.22	38.74
1.0 M NaCl	117.29	117.73	118.33	118.85	35.02	37.01	38.31	38.82
0.05 M NaBr	118.30	119.04	119.79	120.60	36.12	38.46	39.76	40.23
0.1 M NaBr	119.36	120.11	120.84	121.65	36.52	38.46	40.12	40.68
0.5 M NaBr	120.97	122.03	123.05	124.28	36.83	39.16	40.45	40.99
1.0 M NaBr	121.98	122.86	123.76	124.50	37.15	39.45	40.77	41.40
0.05 M KCl	116.11	116.66	117.12	117.63	35.11	36.12	38.41	39.29
0.5 M KCl	118.15	118.80	119.41	119.92	37.22	38.23	39.38	40.53
0.05 M KBr	120.84	121.47	122.23	122.81	37.11	38.21	39.42	40.29
0.5 M KBr	124.41	125.32	126.21	126.93	39.22	40.33	41.41	42.56

square fitting of the equation

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + S_v C \quad (2)$$

where ϕ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and S_v is experimental slope. The ϕ_v^0 and S_v values are presented in Table 1.

The ϕ_v^0 value in water in present investigation is 112.07 cm³ mol⁻¹ at 298.15 K which is in good agreement with reported value of 112.04 reported by Millero *et al.*⁷. Although 111.9⁸, 111.7⁹ and 112.2¹⁰ are also reported. Recently Nikam *et al.*¹ reported the ϕ_v^0 value of glucose in water at 298.15 K as 112.03 cm³ mol⁻¹.

The ϕ_v^0 values of glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr solutions are large and positive. This indicates the presence of strong solute-solvent interactions. It is further observed that ϕ_v^0 in all systems increase slightly with increase in temperature suggesting decrease in solute-solvent interactions at elevated temperatures. The ϕ_v^0 values of glucose in aqueous solution in presence of added electrolytes are higher than those for glucose in pure water. The ϕ_v^0 are positive and increase in solutions with increasing concentration of each electrolyte. This suggests that the structure-making tendency of glucose is enhanced in the presence of ions of electrolyte. The ϕ_v^0 values of glucose in aqueous NaBr are always higher than those in aqueous NaCl. The ϕ_v^0 values of glucose in aqueous KBr are higher than those in aqueous KCl presumably due to introduction of voluminous Br⁻ ion.

The relative viscosity (η_r) data of glucose solutions in

water as well as in aqueous alkali solutions are analysed with the help of equation

$$\eta_r = 1 + BC \quad (3)$$

The Fig. 2 gives representative graphs of η_r versus C for glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl at 298.15 K. Simi-

Fig. 2. η_r versus C for glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl at 298.15 K : (◆) 0 M NaCl; (■) 0.05 M NaCl; (Δ) 0.1 M NaCl; (○) 0.5 M NaCl; (*) 1 M NaCl.

lar plots have been obtained for other solutions at all temperatures. The values of B obtained from the slopes of these plots are listed in Table 2. The B values are positive for glucose solutions in water and in aqueous

Table 2. B Values of glucose in water and in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr solutions at different temperatures

Glucose solution in	B (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)			
	298.15 K	303.15 K	308.15 K	313.15 K
Water	0.534	0.506	0.486	0.466
0.05 M NaCl	0.512	0.487	0.464	0.441
0.1 M NaCl	0.492	0.468	0.448	0.429
0.5 M NaCl	0.451	0.437	0.427	0.419
1.0 M NaCl	0.445	0.429	0.417	0.403
0.05 M NaBr	0.524	0.520	0.516	0.508
0.1 M NaBr	0.497	0.495	0.493	0.483
0.5 M NaBr	0.493	0.475	0.459	0.444
1.0 M NaBr	0.475	0.442	0.404	0.359
0.05 M KCl	0.400	0.389	0.318	0.369
0.5 M KCl	0.385	0.372	0.353	0.338
0.05 M KBr	0.465	0.450	0.439	0.429
0.5 M KBr	0.435	0.431	0.428	0.423

NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr at all temperatures which suggest that glucose acts as structure promoter in these solutions. The B values of glucose solutions in aqueous NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr are lower than those in pure water. This could be explained on the basis that electrolyte is hydrated^{1,2} and reacts with glucose. This leaves less water for sugar molecules for hydration. The positive B and negative dB/dT ¹¹ values in all solutions studied in the present investigation, make glucose as a structure promoter.

Experimental

Water was distilled in quick fit apparatus over alkaline KMnO₄ followed by further distillation over H₂SO₄. The conductance of this distilled water was 5×10^{-6} mhos cm⁻¹. NaBr was purchased from Loba Chemie Indo-Australan Co. with purity greater than 99%. NaCl, KCl and KBr were procured from E. Merck with purity ranging between 99.5 and 99.8%. All these electrolytes were vacuum dried and used without further purification. Glucose was supplied by General Chemical Division, Allied Chemical Corporation, Morrystone MJ, USA with purity 99.8%. The glucose solutions of different molarities were prepared by dissolving accurately weighed amount of glu-

cose in (0.05, 0.1, 0.5 and 1.0 M) aqueous solutions of NaCl, NaBr, KCl and KBr. These solutions were allowed to stand for some time to attain thermal equilibrium with atmosphere. Densities of glucose solutions in water and in aqueous alkali halides were measured using bicapillary pycnometer, with an accuracy of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ g/cm³ as described previously^{12,13}. The pycnometer was mounted in thermostated water bath with thermal stability of ± 0.01 K.

The viscosity measurements were made using a suspended level Ubbelohde viscometer^{14,15}. The viscometer was clamped vertically in the bath and 25 cc of glucose solution was added from a calibrated burette. The viscometer was calibrated with triple distilled water using the viscosity and density values reported by Marsh¹⁶. Viscosity values were determined using the relation

$$\eta_1/\eta_2 = \rho_1 t_1 / \rho_2 t_2 \quad (4)$$

where η_1 , ρ_1 , t_1 and η_2 , ρ_2 , t_2 are viscosity, density and flow time of solvent and solution, respectively. The flow time was measured with an electronic stop watch (accuracy of ± 0.01 s). A viscometer was selected having a flow time of 250 to 300 s for redistilled water at 298.15 K. Since all flow times were greater than 200 s, and capillary radius (0.5 mm) was for less than its length (50–60 mm), the kinetic energy correction was found to be negligible. Accuracy of the viscosity measurements was ± 0.001 mPa.s.

References

1. P. S. Nikam, H. R. Ansari and M. Hasan, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 344.
2. P. S. Nikam, H. R. Ansari and M. Hasan, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2000, **87**, 97.
3. P. S. Nikam, H. R. Ansari and M. Hasan, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2000, **84**, 169.
4. P. S. Nikam, H. R. Ansari and M. Hasan, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.*, 1998, **20**, 5.
5. J. B. Taylor and J. S. Rowlinson, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, **57**, 1183.
6. F. Kawaizumi, B. Nisho, H. Nomura and Y. Migahara, *J. Chem. Thermodynamics*, 1981, **13**, 89.
7. P. S. Nikam, T. B. Pawar, A. B. Sawant and M. Hasan, *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2006, **126**, 19.
8. P. S. Nikam, M. Hasan, M. R. P. Shewale and A. B. Sawant, *J. Solution Chem.*, 2003, **32**, 987.
9. P. S. Nikam, B. S. Jagdale, A. B. Sawant and M. Hasan, *J.*

- Chem. Eng. Data*, 2000, **45**, 214.
10. P. S. Nikam and A. B. Nikumbh, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2002, **47**, 400.
 11. K. N. Marsh, "Recommended Reference Materials for the Realization of Physico-chemical Properties", Blackwell Scientific Publications, Oxford, UK, 1987.
 12. A. L. Surdro, C. Shine and F. J. Millero, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1978, **23**, 197.
 13. F. Frank, J. R. Ravenhill and D. S. Reid, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1972, **1**, 3.
 14. H. Hoiland and H. Holvik, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1978, **7**, 587.
 15. J. T. Edward and F. Shahidi, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 807.
 16. P. S. Nikam and A. R. Hiray, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.*, 1988, **26**, 37.